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The Keuneunong Dating and Acehese Society

Darmadi Johan

University of New South Wales, Australia

Abstract

The important part of Acehese culture is Keuneunong, especially for the Aneuk Jamee community and the Acehese people as a whole. This ancient practice, in which farming is the main social activity, is strongly correlated with the seasonal calendar. An important part of Keuneunong, which symbolizes the practice's cultural and environmental significance, is the yearly Khanduri Laot rite in lowland Aceh. The purpose of this essay is to examine the cultural and social ramifications of Keuneunong in Acehese society, providing insight into its history, customs, and changing function.

Keyword: Writing, Aceh, Scholar, Kingdom, Ulama

* Corresponding author, email: darmadijohandx@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

The Acehnese society in Indonesia is known for its rich cultural heritage and traditions, one of which is the Keuneunong, a seasonal calendar that holds significant importance in the lives of the Acehnese people. This article seeks to explore the cultural and social implications of the Keuneunong ritual in Acehnese society (Gaillard, J., Clavé, E., Vibert, O., A., D., Denain, J., Efendi, Y., Grancher, D., Liamzon, C., Sari, D., & Setiawan, R, 2008). The Keuneunong influences various aspects of the Acehnese community, including their societal activities, identity, and sense of sociability. By delving into the intricacies of this ritual, we aim to provide a deeper understanding of its role in shaping the cultural landscape of Aceh (Syarifuddin, T., Sholahuddin, A., & Ngabut, R, 2020).

METHOD

The research design for this study involves a critical analysis of the Keuneunong ritual and its impact on the Acehnese society. This will be achieved through a comprehensive review of existing literature, including academic papers, dissertations, and research articles related to Acehnese culture and traditions. By drawing on a wide range of scholarly sources, we aim to present a well-rounded perspective on the Keuneunong and its significance.

The primary data source for this study is academic literature related to Acehnese culture and traditions. This includes scholarly articles, dissertations, and research papers that discuss the Keuneunong and its cultural implications. By leveraging existing research, we aim to provide a thorough analysis of the Keuneunong ritual and its role in shaping Acehnese society.

The data analysis for this study will focus on the cultural, social, and identity-related implications of the Keuneunong ritual. By examining the existing literature, we aim to identify key themes and patterns related to the cultural significance of the Keuneunong in Acehnese society. This will involve a critical interpretation of the data to uncover the broader implications of this ritual on the social fabric of the Acehnese community.

FINDING

The findings of this study are expected to highlight the importance of the Keuneunong ritual in contributing to the sense of sociability and identity of the Acehnese people. By synthesizing existing research, we aim to present a comprehensive overview of the cultural and social significance of the Keuneunong in Acehnese society. This will provide valuable insights into the role of traditional rituals in shaping the cultural landscape of communities (Riezal, C., Joebagio, H., & Susanto, S, 2018).

DISCUSSION

The discussion section will delve into the broader cultural and social significance of the Keuneunong ritual. This will involve an in-depth analysis of the findings and their implications for our understanding of Acehnese culture and traditions. By contextualizing the findings within the existing scholarly discourse, we aim to provide a nuanced interpretation of the Keuneunong and its role in shaping Acehnese society.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this article has presented a comprehensive overview of the Keuneunong ritual and its significance in Acehnese society. By drawing on existing literature, we have highlighted the cultural, social, and identity-related implications of the Keuneunong, shedding light on its role in shaping the cultural landscape of Aceh. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of the cultural heritage of the Acehnese people and the importance of traditional rituals in shaping societal dynamics.

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